

Improving French Plutonium Inventory Assessment via Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

The French nuclear fuel cycle strategy relies on reprocessing spent fuel and recycling plutonium in MOX-fueled PWRs, with plans to deploy fast reactors in the future. Accurate assessment of current plutonium inventories is crucial for evaluating future recycling strategies, but historical operational uncertainties significantly affect stock estimates. Previous Monte Carlo studies showed that uncertainties in plutonium inventories exceeded 10%, limiting the reliability of prospective analyses. This work employs a Bayesian methodology, using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to reduce these uncertainties by incorporating historical spent fuel inventory data provided by the French Agency for Radioactive Waste Management (ANDRA). We model the French PWR fleet using the CLASS fuel cycle simulation code, introducing a key parameter to reconcile simulations with historical data, a variability factor that accounts for a reduced number of MOX assemblies compared to the nominal strategy. The Adaptive Metropolis algorithm efficiently explores the 19-dimensional parameter space. Results demonstrate a four-fold reduction in plutonium inventory uncertainties compared to standard Monte Carlo approaches, reducing operational uncertainties to levels comparable to nuclear data (approximately 2-3%). The variability factor is precisely estimated at $60\% \pm 3\%$. However, we identify a systematic bias (up to 10%) due to the full-core loading assumption in CLASS, which exceeds the reduced posterior uncertainties. While this study successfully demonstrates the potential of the Bayesian approach for uncertainty reduction, addressing the bias due to the batch loading assumption remains essential to improve the accuracy of historical inventory assessments.

Keywords: Fuel cycle simulations, Plutonium, Metropolis-Hastings, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

The French nuclear fuel cycle strategy has historically been, and remains, based on the reprocessing of spent fuel (SF) [1]. The recovered plutonium is currently used to fabricate MOX fuel for use in Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs). In the medium term, this strategy aims to recycle plutonium from MOX fuel previously irradiated in PWR, with the long-term goal of the deployment of Fast Reactors (FRs).

Given the complexity of nuclear material evolution and reactor operation over decades, analyzing such a fuel cycle requires specialized computational tools. We employ the CLASS code [2] to address these challenges, an open-source package developed by French CNRS/IN2P3. The CLASS framework models various facilities, including reactors (both PWRs and FRs), cooling pools, material stocks, fabrication and separation plants. Using available inventories of fissile and fertile materials, the fabrication plant generates fresh fuel for the reactors according to a loading model, which is then followed by fuel depletion simulations.

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However, evaluating future recycling strategies requires careful consideration of uncertainties stemming from historical data, particularly those affecting current stock composition (both mass and isotope). In earlier studies [3], a Monte Carlo method was used to propagate these parameter uncertainties, showing that the uncertainty in the plutonium mass within the stocks exceeded 10%. We adopt a Bayesian approach that incorporates new data using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to reduce this uncertainty. This widely used method for sampling from probability distributions has already proven effective in other nuclear applications, such as estimating boiling water reactor model parameters [4].

To implement this Bayesian framework effectively, we first need to establish a comprehensive model of the French nuclear fuel cycle. The following section describes how we represent the historical fleet using CLASS, including key modeling choices and necessary parameter adjustments.

2. FUEL CYCLE MODELING WITH CLASS

2.1. Reactors and Reprocessing Modeling

We model the 58 French PWRs in CLASS, considering their historical core management strategies, which are characterized by fuel type, uranium enrichment or plutonium content, target burnup, and batch size. A load factor is associated with each reactor (data taken from [5]). Our modeling approach differs from reality in one key aspect: CLASS reactors renew their entire core in a single step, unlike actual reactors, which perform batch reloads. To account for reactors partially loaded with MOX, we create two independent CLASS reactors: one for UOX assemblies and one for MOX assemblies. Their fabrication and evolution are not coupled. Following discharge from reactors, SF enters a cooling pool where it remains for a specified period before becoming available for reprocessing. The reprocessing plant operates with a fixed annual capacity, transferring recovered plutonium to the separated plutonium stock. This plutonium subsequently feeds the MOX fabrication plant.

2.2. A New Parameter: *Hybride_Variability*

During initial testing, we observed an unexpected discrepancy: the “Hybride” core management strategy (core partially fueled with 5.3%Pu MOX fuel - 35 GWd/t [6]) required a burnup above 55 GWd/t to match the reference spent MOX inventory [7]. The observed spent fuel inventory at a given time is the product of the reloading frequency (inversely proportional to burnup) and the number of assemblies loaded per cycle. This higher required burnup indicates an overestimation in the assumed number of MOX assemblies loaded per cycle. To address this overestimation, we introduce the *Hybride_Variability* parameter, defined as the ratio $N_{real}/N_{nominal}$ (actual to nominal number of loaded MOX assemblies). Based on this ratio, we adjust the UOX and MOX masses in the reactors. Literature supports this via a “Hybride” variant using 24 MOX assemblies instead of 48 [6]. Accordingly, we set a 50 - 100% range, spanning from all cores with 24 MOX assemblies to all cores with 48 MOX assemblies.

2.3. Additional Plutonium

Beyond adjusting assembly loadings through the *Hybride Variability* parameter, our initial simulations revealed another discrepancy. We observed that some MOX loadings failed due to a shortage of plutonium in the separated plutonium stock. To address this issue, we created an *ad hoc* plutonium reserve that the MOX fabrication plant can access when necessary. We carefully monitored the mass of plutonium drawn from this reserve, and its implications are discussed in Section 4.2.

3. METROPOLIS-HASTINGS ALGORITHM TO ASSESS UNCERTAINTIES

With the fuel cycle model established and key parameters identified, we now detail how the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm leverages historical data to refine our estimation of uncertainties.

3.1. Presentation of the Algorithm

From a Bayesian perspective, the probability of a statement x represents the level of confidence in that statement. Consequently, probabilities can be updated using new data y as follows:

$$\pi(x | y) \propto \mathcal{L}(x, y) \times \pi(x) \quad (1)$$

where $\pi(x)$, $\mathcal{L}(x, y)$, and $\pi(x | y)$ are the prior probability, the likelihood, and the posterior probability.

The Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm enables sampling from posterior distributions by combining prior information with the likelihood of new data. As a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm, it constructs a Markov chain (a sequence of events where the probability of the next event depends only on the current state) that asymptotically converges toward the target posterior distribution.

In practice, the algorithm randomly draws a candidate vector x_{test} from a transition probability in the neighborhood of the previous vector x_i . The posterior probability of x_{test} is then calculated, and the candidate is accepted with probability α , which depends on the ratio of posterior probabilities:

$$p(x_{i+1} = x_{test}) = \alpha = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(x_{test}, y) \times \pi(x_{test})}{\mathcal{L}(x_i, y) \times \pi(x_i)} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad p(x_{i+1} = x_i) = 1 - \alpha \quad (2)$$

To apply the MH algorithm for quantifying uncertainties related to the French fleet, we define the prior distributions, likelihood function, and transition probability used in the following section.

3.2. Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm applied to the French Historical Fleet

3.2.1. Likelihood

The likelihood of a parameter vector x accounts for both the SF data from ANDRA (French Agency for Radioactive Waste Management) [7] and the amount of additional plutonium needed in the scenario:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y) \propto \mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{ANDRA}}) \times \mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{Additional Pu}}) \quad (3)$$

Table I presents the SF mass (UOX and MOX) provided by ANDRA data for 6 different years. Assuming independence of these values, the likelihood associated with the SF inventory is:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{ANDRA}}) \propto e^{-\chi^2/2} \quad \text{with} \quad \chi^2 = \sum_{k \in (\text{UOX}, \text{MOX})} \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{(\text{Inv_CLASS}^{k,i}(x) - y_{\text{ANDRA}}^{k,i})^2}{\sigma_{k,i}^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\text{Inv_CLASS}^{k,i}(x)$ and $y_{\text{ANDRA}}^{k,i}$ are the CLASS-simulated SF mass with parameters x and ANDRA data for the SF mass in stock k (UOX or MOX) at the i -th date. We test $\sigma_{k,i} = 0.05 \times y_{\text{ANDRA}}^{k,i}$ and $\sigma_{k,i} = 0.1 \times y_{\text{ANDRA}}^{k,i}$. Results are respectively named ANDRA5% and ANDRA10%.

Table I. SF inventories according to ANDRA (tHM). [7]

SF type	2002	2004	2007	2010	2013	2016
UOX	10500	10900	11745	12274	12320	11987
MOX	520	700	1018	1287	1540	1840

As discussed in Section 2, the need for additional plutonium stock should be minimal. Therefore, we defined the likelihood component $\mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{Additional Pu}})$ to favor simulations with limited need for additional plutonium. This likelihood remains constant up to $\text{AddPu}_{\text{threshold}} = 25$ t of additional plutonium

(threshold value discussed in Section 4.2), then decreases exponentially:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{Additional Pu}}) \propto \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \text{AddPu_CLASS}(x) < \text{AddPu}_{\text{threshold}} \\ e^{-(\text{AddPu_CLASS}(x) - \text{AddPu}_{\text{threshold}}) / \lambda} & \text{if } \text{AddPu_CLASS}(x) > \text{AddPu}_{\text{threshold}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $\text{AddPu_CLASS}(x)$ is the additional plutonium needed in the simulation with parameter vector x . We do not impose a hard cutoff $\mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{Additional Pu}}) = 0$ for $\text{AddPu_CLASS}(x) > \text{AddPu}_{\text{threshold}}$ because the MH algorithm requires the computation of posterior probability ratios, which would be undefined in such cases. We set $\lambda = 0.007$ to ensure that $\mathcal{L}(x, y_{\text{Additional Pu}})$ rapidly drops to near-zero values.

3.2.2. Prior distributions

We define prior distributions for the 19 identified parameters, with characteristics provided in Tables II and III. The "BU_ ..." parameters are the discharge burnup of the different historical core management strategies. We employ two types of distributions (Gaussian or uniform) based on available information.

For the parameters listed in Table II, precise values were found in the literature, therefore, we choose to center Gaussian distributions on these mean values. The standard deviation for burnups is set to 1 GWd/t, justified by confidence in data sources and the likelihood that the main source of error arises from rounding values to the nearest integer. For separation plant capacities, since reprocessing contracts are multiannual and actual annual production may vary, we selected 50 tHM/year (approximately 5% of the annual capacity) as an acceptable standard deviation.

Table II. Gaussian distributions characteristics.

Parameter	Unit	Mean	Standard deviation
BU_STD900 [6], BU_STD1300 [6]	GWd/t	33	1
BU_STD1450 [6], BU_GEMMES [6]	GWd/t	43	1
BU_GARANÇE [6]	GWd/t	42	1
BU_CYCLADES [8], BU_ALCADE [8], BU_PARITE_MOX [8]	GWd/t	46	1
BU_TIERS_UOX [6]	GWd/t	32	1
BU_TIERS_MOX [6]	GWd/t	36	1
BU_HYBRIDE_UOX [6]	GWd/t	40	1
BU_HYBRIDE_MOX [6]	GWd/t	35	1
BU_PARITE_UOX [8]	GWd/t	44	1
Separation Plant Capacity (1994-2010) [9]	tHM/year	850	50
Separation Plant Capacity (2010-...) [9]	tHM/year	1050	50

For the parameters listed in Table III, where no precise values were found in the literature, we choose uniform distributions with bounds defining plausible value ranges.

3.2.3. Transition probability

While the MH algorithm theoretically converges to the target distribution, achieving this in practice critically depends on the choice of transition probability. The classical approach uses a multivariate Gaussian distribution centered on x_i to generate the test vector x_{test} . However, selecting appropriate

Table III. Uniform distributions characteristics.

Parameter	Unit	Minimum	Maximum
Separation Plant Capacity (...-1994)	tHM/year	0	500
Reprocessing efficiency	%	90	100
UOX cooling time	year	0	10
Hybride_Variability	%	50	100

standard deviations for different parameters is crucial: if the acceptance rate is too low or too high, the algorithm either explores too slowly or fails to explore the parameter space effectively. To address this challenge, we employ the Adaptive Metropolis (AM) algorithm [10], where the transition probability is:

$$x_{test} | x_i \sim \mathcal{N}(x_i, \Sigma), \quad \text{with} \quad \Sigma \propto \begin{cases} \Sigma_0 & \text{if } i < i_0 \\ \text{Covariance}(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_i) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Although this adaptation means the process is no longer strictly Markovian, as the transition probability now depends on the chain's history rather than just x_i , and the algorithm is still expected to converge [10]. This approach achieves more efficient convergence because the proposal distribution accounts for the chain's history. It adapts its scale and orientation according to correlations between parameters. We use a constant diagonal Σ_0 for initial iterations while accumulating sufficient vectors.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Algorithm Convergence and Updated Parameters Values

Despite using AM, convergence to the correct distribution can be challenging, especially depending on the choice of the initial parameter vector x_0 . To ensure robust convergence, we launched six parallel chains from six randomly selected initial points. The Gelman-Rubin statistic \hat{R} , commonly used to assess Markov chain convergence by comparing between-chain and within-chain variance [11], serves as our convergence metric, with $\hat{R} < 1.1$ usually considered a target condition. As with any Monte Carlo process, initial iterations must be discarded, therefore, we chose to discard the first 200 iterations for each chain to minimize \hat{R} . The analysis is based on 13,200 posterior samples (2,200 samples \times 6 chains), achieving $\hat{R} = 1.03$ and $\hat{R} = 1.08$ respectively for MOX and UOX stock distribution.

Having established convergence, we examine how the algorithm updates our parameter estimates. The posterior mean values remain close to prior ones for Gaussian distributions, with the maximum difference in mean value being 0.6 GWd/t for burnups. This stability confirms our confidence in literature values while slightly refining estimates. The MH algorithm significantly refines the parameter estimates for uniform priors. In particular, the Hybride_Variability parameter converges to a mean value of 60% with a standard deviation of 3% (compared to the prior uniform distribution between 50% and 100%). This precise quantification represents a significant improvement in our understanding of historical operations.

4.2. Additional Plutonium Need

The additional plutonium requirement stems from bias caused by full-core batch loading in CLASS simulations. To quantify this bias, we created a simulation in which each real reactor is modeled by several CLASS reactors, each of which models a fraction of the core, and the loading dates of the CLASS reactors are desynchronized by a fraction of the nominal irradiation time. While this simulation runs

20 times longer than the standard one (1 hour versus 3 minutes), which makes it impractical for the MH algorithm (approximately $2000 \text{ simulations} \times 1 \text{ h} > 2 \text{ months}$), it provides crucial validation. To evaluate the bias, we ran a classic and a detailed simulation, using the same mean posterior parameters.

This detailed analysis reveals that some assemblies in the first cores have reduced residence times (one or two thirds of nominal), making them available for reprocessing earlier. Figure 1(a) shows that batch simulation leads to SF assemblies being reprocessed earlier than in our simplified model. Furthermore, since 1987, the progressive introduction of MOX fuel by thirds of the core (16, then 32, and finally 48 assemblies) creates additional timing discrepancies. Figure 1(b) shows that classical simulation requires more plutonium because reactors are assumed to load all 48 MOX assemblies directly at the MOX introduction date. This leads to both premature plutonium demand for MOX fabrication and delayed fuel reprocessing. Consequently, additional plutonium is required in the classical simulation. However, this additional mass remains below 10 t (8 t in Figure 1(c)). The bias on total plutonium mass is even smaller (Figure 1(c)) because more MOX fuel (consuming plutonium) has been loaded. The bias observed in specific stocks (UOX, MOX, separated plutonium) is comparable in magnitude: between 5 and 10 t (up to 10%). This represents a systematic bias requiring correction.

Among the 13,200 accepted simulations, the mean value of required additional plutonium is 6.8 t with a standard deviation of 3.3 t. Since the threshold $AddPu_{threshold} = 25 \text{ t}$ in our likelihood definition (Section 3.2.1) is well above this range, it did not affect or constrain the posterior distribution in practice.

Figure 1. Comparison of classic and batch simulation.

4.3. Plutonium Inventories and Uncertainties

Our parameter updates directly impact the estimated plutonium inventories. Table IV provides the mean and standard deviation of plutonium inventory distributions comparing the MH algorithm with a standard Monte Carlo approach. Only minor differences are observed between mean values, indicating consistency between approaches. However, the crucial improvement lies in uncertainty reduction: the MH algorithm reduces the standard deviations by 4 with ANDRA5%. The uncertainties are also substantially reduced in ANDRA10% by a factor close to 3.5, showing limited sensitivity to $\sigma_{k,i}$. This dramatic improvement is clearly visible in Figure 2, where posterior stocks show tighter distributions. Remarkably, the uncertainties obtained with the MH algorithm due to operational parameters are now of the same magnitude (a few percent) as those from nuclear data [12].

Nevertheless, the identified bias due to the absence of batch loading (Section 4.2: up to 10%) exceeds uncertainties due to operational parameters. Given this bias and our arbitrary choice of $\sigma_{k,i}$, the uncertainties in Table IV should be considered carefully; this work provides a proof of concept for the methodology's potential.

Table IV. Plutonium inventories distributions in 2020.

Plutonium in		All cycle	UOX SF	MOX SF
Standard Monte-Carlo (priors)	Mean (t)	348	115	131
	Standard deviation (%)	3.8	14.7	8.7
MH algorithm - ANDRA5% (posteriors)	Mean (t)	335	113	121
	Standard deviation (%)	1.1	3.4	2.0
MH algorithm - ANDRA10% (posteriors)	Mean (t)	337	116	121
	Standard deviation (%)	1.1	4.3	2.6

Figure 2. Comparison of SF stocks evolution with priors and posteriors parameters.

Beyond mass inventories, the MH algorithm also provides access to plutonium isotopic composition. Figure 3 displays the distributions of plutonium mean quality (the fraction of fissile isotopes) in SF stocks, providing essential information for future plutonium recycling studies.

Figure 3. Distribution for plutonium mean quality in UOX and MOX SF in 2020.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Properly accounting for historical data uncertainties is essential for accurate evaluation of nuclear fuel cycle strategies. This study successfully applied a Bayesian methodology using the Metropolis-Hastings

algorithm to reduce historical uncertainties in French nuclear fuel cycle simulations. By incorporating historical SF inventory data, the method achieved a four-fold reduction in uncertainties in plutonium inventories estimates compared to standard Monte Carlo approaches. These reduced uncertainties are now comparable in magnitude to nuclear data uncertainties.

Furthermore, we introduced and precisely quantified the *Hybride_Variability* parameter. This parameter proved essential for accurate alignment between simulations and historical data.

However, our work also identified and quantified a significant systematic bias arising from the full-core batch loading assumption in CLASS simulations. This bias, which is larger than the final posterior uncertainties calculated by the algorithm, has now become the dominant source of error. While this study demonstrates the effectiveness of the Bayesian methodology as a proof-of-concept, it reveals that future efforts must prioritize correcting this bias to assess historical inventories and their uncertainties accurately.

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